

INCREASE TRAFFIC SAFETY AT RAILWAY CROSSINGS

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Annotation: In this thesis, it is discussed about the measures to prevent various hazards that may occur in railways and railway crossings.

Key words: railway, intersections, preventive measures, various hazards.

As we know, railways are means of transport that bring us closer together. In order to prevent various hazards at railway crossings, measures are taken continuously.

The following devices are used to ensure traffic safety at railway crossings:

1) the device for blocking the carriageway of the highway and stopping the movement of vehicles (road users) through the railway crossing.

When the railway crossing is equipped with crossing signaling, the barriers are considered a duplicate device and prevent unauthorized passage of vehicles (traffic participants) at the railway crossing.

Barriers are divided into the following types according to the actuation methods: automatic - when the train approaches the railway crossing, when it enters the railway section and when the red signals (lights) of the crossing traffic lights are turned on, the barrier barriers are closed (horizontal) during the calculated time is done automatically. When the train clears the railway crossing, the barriers of the barrier automatically move to the open (vertical) position. In this case, the red signals (lights) of the intersection traffic light will turn off;

semi-automated - switching of the barriers to the closed (horizontal) position is carried out automatically when the train enters the approach section, or when the railway station attendant opens the signal to the train, merges the route, or presses a special button. Opening of the barriers of the barrier (moving them to a vertical position) is carried out by the crossing guard by pressing a special button;

electrified (electric-barriers) - the barriers are moved to the closed (horizontal) position by pressing a special button after the crossing guard receives a notification signal. Opening of the barriers of the barrier (moving them to a vertical position) is carried out by returning the special button to the initial position by the crossing guard after the railway crossing is cleared of the train; mechanized - barriers have a mechanical transmission, with the help of which the crossing guard manually switches the barriers to the open (vertical) and closed (horizontal) positions;

horizontal-rotating (spare) - barricades are placed parallel to the carriageway in the open state. In order to stop the movement of vehicles, the crossing guard (or another employee acting as a crossing guard) blocks the traffic section of the highway by turning them by hand;

2) a device controlled by a crossing guard (or another worker acting as a crossing guard), which, when turned on, prohibits a train from entering a railway crossing;

3) a device that prohibits the movement of vehicles and road users through a railway crossing with the activation of traffic lights and sound signals when a train approaches.

All equipment will be dismantled at the closed railway crossing. When the use of the level crossing is stopped for a short period of time, the automatic level crossing signal is turned off during its closed period, and the manually operated horizontal-swinging backup barrier gates are closed to vehicular traffic and locked. The procedure for turning off automatic devices at a railway crossing is determined by the owner of the infrastructure or the owner of branch railways. On the roads leading to closed railway crossings, the owner of the infrastructure or the owner of branch railways, in agreement with the owner of the highway crossing this railway crossing, must be equipped with platforms for vehicles to turn around.

It is the responsibility of the owner of the infrastructure and the owner of the branch railways to inform about the closure of the railway crossing. The notification procedure, as well as the procedure for dismantling, storing or reusing the equipment, devices and equipment of the closed railway crossings, is determined by the owner of the infrastructure or the owner of branch railways in agreement.

Simultaneously with the development of projects for the construction of secondary roads and the development of transport links, the owner of the infrastructure and the owner of branch railways together with the owners of

highways can replace existing level crossings with overpasses or replace highways with railways.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be noted that serious attention should be paid to all railway activities, otherwise the consequences will be bad. Whether the railways are operating or not, their condition should be under constant control.

Использованная литература:

1. Railroad Crossing by L. Gaan Paperback.
<https://www.betterworldbooks.com/product/detail/railroad-crossing-9781795191159>
2. <https://kun.uz/uz/news/2020/03/02/temir-yol-kesishmalaridan-foydalanish-qoidalari-elon-qilindi>
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5. Railroaded By Richard White <https://shepherd.com/book/railroaded>

